

THE IMPACT OF HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT FUNCTIONS IN ACHIEVING COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGES: A CASE STUDY OF JORDAN PUBLIC UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

This study aimed to show the impact of human resources management in achieving competitive advantage, and to identify the dimensions of human resources management and its definitions and the contribution of human resources in raising the efficiency of employee performance in organizations.

Keywords: Human Resources, Competitive Advantage, Low Cost Leadership, Quality Advantage, Differentiation Advantage

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the world is experiencing rapid, highly complicated and multiple changes with tangled elements which entirely began to exercise pressures on business organizations which in turn represent a threat for the existence and survival of these organizations. This lead the organizations to reconsider their methods in performing their works to achieve the organizations' purposes, to predict changes, to develop their internal environments, to adapt to the external environment, and to efficiently and effectively achieve their strategic goals.

Nowadays, the attitudes of higher education institutions in advanced nations are toward formulating a new intellectual framework through accommodating current changes and transferences. This require rethinking by the role that became inevitably be played by higher education institutions in teaching and preparing the future generations, and to rethink by their philosophy, message and their educational programs. Therefore, universities seek survival and development within market by developing general strategies to achieve their goals as these universities face increased challenges, such as increasing their gains and returns, increasing employee's satisfaction, improving their services, increasing the levels of their educational and administrative needs, improving competition on both the local and the international levels, and enhancing the diversity of work force and its change 12 (Arouet, 2009)

Problem of the Study

Past studies investigated the relationship between the above variables (i.e. HR practices and competitive advantage); however, to the researcher knowledge, no study in Jordan public universities context has investigated the direct effect of HRM on achieving competitive advantages to overcome the aforementioned challenges faced by Jordan universities. Hence, the aim of this study is to explore and investigates the direct relationship between HR practices and competitive advantage within Jordanian public universities.

Aims of the Study

This study aims to investigate the impact of HRM practices on achieving competitive advantage within Jordanian public universities; therefore, this study intends to achieve the following objectives:

- 1) Constructing a theoretical framework for the intellectual pillars and the cognitive bases of the main functions of HRM and competitive advantage.
- 2) To diagnosis levels of HRM practice for its functions within Jordanian public universities.
- 3) To explain the suggestions that may contribute to HRM success and activation in achieving competitive advantage for the longest possible term.
- 4) To identify how to improve HRM practicing in Jordan public universities.
- 5) To examine levels of competitive advantages achieved by Jordan public universities.

The Main Hypothesis

The following main hypothesis is designed to answer the study questions based on the study problem and aim: Hypothesis 1: There is no statistically significant impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of HRM practices (Planning, Recruitment and selection, Training and Developing, Compensation and wages, Performance management) on the Competitive Advantage (Low Cost Leadership, quality Advantage, Differentiation advantage,) in the Governmental Jordanian Universities.

From this main hypothesis, the following sub hypotheses were derived:

Hypothesis 1.1: There is no statistically significant impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of the HRM practices (Planning, Recruitment and selection, Training and Developing, Compensation and wages, Performance management) on the Low-Cost Leadership advantage) in the Governmental Jordanian Universities.

Hypothesis 1.2: There is no statistically significant impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of the HRM practices (Planning, Recruitment and selection, Training and Developing, Compensation and wages, Performance management) on the quality advantage in the Governmental Jordanian Universities.

Hypothesis 1.3: There is no statistically significant impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of the HRM practices (Planning, Recruitment and selection, Training and Developing, Compensation and wages, Performance management) on the Differentiation advantage in the Governmental Jordanian Universities.

Study Model Based on the study questions and hypotheses, figure 1 shows the study model that investigates the role of human resource in creating competitive advantage.

Figure 1: Research Model

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Concept of Human Resource Management

The concept of Human Resource Management implies to the management of individuals at the work place.

HRM is thus a process that bounds individuals with their respective organizations and thus aids both employees as well as firms to easily attain each other's objectives and goals. Various practices, processes, and goals are designed with an aim of helping both an organization and its employees to achieve their set goals⁴⁰ (Malkawi, Obeidat & Halasa, 2017).

The HRM concept is defined in different ways like for instance; it is defined as being the process of managing individuals in firms in a through and structured way. This also encompasses staffing or hiring of people, their retention, and setting of perks and pay as well as performance management.

This is indeed the conventional definition of Human Resource Management while the second definition of the concept is known to encompass the management of individuals in an organization from the macro perspectives. These include the management of individuals in form of —collective relationships between employees and management.

The last approach is known to focus on both the outcomes and objectives of Human Resource Management function. All these implies that the Human Resource function in modern organizations is highly concerned with notions of people development, people enabling, and a focus on the development of employment relationships that is used for both employees and management⁴¹ (Abualoush, Masa' deh, Bataineh & Alrowwad, 2018).

Definition of Human Resources Management Human resource management is known to handle any organizational aspects that affect employees, and these include among other the hiring and firing processes, training, benefits, pay, and even administration. In addition to that, Human Resources can also be tasked with provision of safety procedures, work incentives, vacation or sick days for employees working in Jordanian Public Universities. The aspect of Human Resource Management mostly referred to as HRM is an essential part and parcel of ensuring that a business entity is not only kept alive but successful in its endeavors⁴³ (Naser et al 2017).

Types of Strategies for Human Resource Management

HRM strategies are known to set out what a given firm intends to do regarding its HRM practices and policies and how they ought to be integrated in the business strategy as well as with each other⁵⁸ (Al-Lozi et al. 2019). They are therefore described as being internally and consistent HRM bundles and practices. A strategy should have two major elements namely having strategic objectives which include the things which are supposed to be achieved by strategy and a plan of action which implies to the means which are proposed for the achievement of such objectives.

Major purpose of HRM strategies is thus to help in articulating what a firm intends to do regarding the HRM practices and policies in both the present as well as future⁵⁹ (Arqawi et al. 2018). This implies that there is need for HRM managers to perform extremely well in the present so as they can also succeed during the future. It is also important to note that HRM strategies should always aim at meeting both the human and business needs in a given organization. It is prudent for Public Jordanian universities to note that since each and every organization is different from each other, then this implies that there is need for the HRM strategies to be different as well. This is because there is no standard strategy that can be effectively used to fit all organizations across the world. In essence HRM strategies are classified as being general which include high performance workings and specific strategies that are associated to different aspects of HRM such as development, reward and learning.

Employee Resourcing Strategy

Employee Resourcing Strategy implies to a process which identifies both the present and future HRM needs for a given organization to attain its goals. It also involves the preparation of plans for finding individuals from within an organization or training problems to help individuals in learning new skills. It is also important to note that employee resourcing is indeed a broad issue other than just recruitment and selection.

Jordanian Public Universities can achieve competitive advantages through the creation of resourcing strategies⁶¹ (Nwachukwu & Chladková, 2017). Employee resourcing thus is therefore very important because it deals with a range of approaches and methods which employers use in resourcing to enable their organizations to become profitable. There are various strategies that are used for the determination of employee resources and these can either come from the internal or external markets of employment.

Training and Human Resources Development

Training can be defined as being an endeavour that is aimed at enhancing or developing additional skills or competencies in employees on the job in order to enhance productivity or performance. Training involves a change in employees' knowledge, skills, or attitude of an individual with resultant enhancement in behaviour⁶² (Altarawneh, 2016). However, it is important for Jordanian Public Universities to put in mind that for any training to become effective, then it has to be effectively planned after carrying out need analysis and ensuring that it is carried out in a conducive learning atmosphere. It is also important for institutions to ensure that in the development of training programs, it is important to keep in both that organizational and individual goals are given utmost considerations. Although it may not be possible for synchronization, the institutions should ensure that the competencies are actually chosen or selected in a manner that creates a win-win situation for both employees and their organizations. In order to create an effective training and human resource strategy, it is important for public universities in Jordan to analyse the needs of an organization to analyse the respective needs of their institutions through putting together or developing a training strategy⁶³ (Al-Mawahreh, 2018). The next step is the identification of the skills gaps and this involves taking a loop at any prevailing gaps in the employee competencies, abilities, skills, and knowledge. There will also be needed to prioritize, plan, and ultimately deliver training.

Competitive Advantage

In the business aspects, competitive advantage implies to the attributes or factors which make it possible for a given firm to yield more affordable or even higher quality products or services as opposed to those offered by its competitors.

A competitive advantage is the referee what actually makes a firm 'services or goods to become more powerful choices for customers. Even though the term of competitive advantage is mostly used in the business world, it is also applied in the universities in ensuring that the best Human Resource Management (HRM) functions are attained (Al-Hawary & Nusair, 2017).

With the prevalence of private universities, there is need for public universities to ensure that they apply the best HRM functions in order to attain or achieve competitive advantages that will ultimately make such institutions to become the best choice for students. The strategies in the achievement of competitive advantage are therefore known to be applicable for any country, individual, or even universities in competitive environments. Competitive advantage cannot be easily achieved by organizations, universities included without putting into consideration the three major determinants. For public universities in Jordan to easily achieve competitive advantages, they need to embrace these three determinants one of them being the benefits that the institution seeks to provide. Such benefits should therefore be what the clients who in this case are the students and other stakeholders in the university need (Obeidat, Tawalbeh & Akour, 2019).

The public universities in Jordan should therefore present or offer real or actual value to the clients that they serve. In order to achieve such competitive advantage, Jordanian public universities should stay up to date with new trends that affect their operations such the use of new technology.

The use of Differentiation Advantage by Public Universities in Jordan to achieve competitive Advantage.

Differentiation advantage implies to instances when a business entity provides customers with better services and products as opposed to its competitors. In essence, it also implies to a set or range of benefits that a firm is capable of providing profitably on a daily basis in its operation which is quite relevant to the customer 's purchasing decisions and which cannot be easily duplicated profitably and routinely by its competitors (Al-najjar, 2016). It also makes use of competitive differentiation which implies to a — strategic positioning tacticl that can be used by an organization in order to undertake to set a range of its services, products, and brands apart from that of its competitors (Almasri et al. 2018). It is prudent to note that positioning statements can be used by the Jordanian Public universities in provision of a basis for not only competitive differentiation but also through the definition of specific advantages provided by a specific reasoning. The use of differentiation strategy by public universities in Jordan is quite beneficial because apart from helping these institutions to develop additional value, they are also quite important because it helps them in the development of loyalty among the stakeholders. This ultimately helps the Jordanian public universities to achieve competitive advantages thus making them become distinguished from the competitors (Yaseen, Dajani & Hasan, 2016). The establishment of this differentiation advantage is quite important for any given organization; public universities in Jordan included because it helps them accomplish its goals and becomes essential for the success of its operations.

The use of the differentiation strategy can help public universities in Jordan to attain competitive advantages in markets that are dominated by the private universities. It can therefore be truly asserted that differentiation advantage is essential for public universities in Jordan because it helps in the creation of value (Obeidat, Tawalbeh & Akour, 2019). This is because when such universities make use of differentiation strategies which focuses on the overall cost values of the products and services that they offer versus similar products and services that are offered by the market, this leads to the creation of value among the clients. This ultimately places value highlights on the durability or savings of the other products. In addition to that, it is also important to note that the use of differentiation advantage helps public universities to compete in various areas other than the use of price alone. In order to easily gain a competitive advantage among the other universities, the Jordanian public universities should focus on the design and quality of the various products and services that they offer without necessarily decreasing the costs. The creation of —product differentiation strategyll by public universities in Jordan can only be successful if it is capable of creating brand loyalty among its customers (Al-Daibat, 2017).

How low cost leadership helps public universities in Jordan

To achieve competitive advantages during this study, it is aimed at identifying whether the Jordanian Public universities have input into practice the competitive aspect to achieve competitive advantage. In the course of the study, it was realized that the Jordanian public universities used the competitive dimensions in achieving the competitive advantages such as delivery, mobility and the cost in order to create an impact on its students and workers (Abu AlRub & Nasrallah, 2017).

In Jordan, it has been noticed that there has been a great competition between the public universities and their very close competitors that is the private universities.

Firstly, in order to achieve the competitive advantage, public universities in Jordan have in turn focused on the reduction of its costs to make their products more affordable to its students and other workers. Due to this advantage of the low costs, it has enabled the Jordanian public universities to outdo their competitors who are the public universities on the market in their service and product production.

Secondly, in order to achieve the competitive advantage by the Jordanian public universities, the universities should be able to get adapted more easily to different levels in the target market. This should be through their ability to get used with the changes in the developments in technology and improvise the services and products according to the students and worker's expectations. Due to this, most Jordanian universities have been able the win more fame than their competitors who are the private universities hence attracting more students countrywide.

Thirdly, the Jordanian public universities have been able to reduce the cost at which they deliver their services and products, hence achieving a competitive advantage. Therefore, to achieve that, they have been able to reach out to the demands of their students and workers to negotiate with them on the prices at which they want their services to be rendered. This has enabled them to become more dominant in the competitive market hence achieving a larger market share making them achieve the customers ' satisfaction easily (Al-Zawahreh, Khasawneh & Al-Jaradat, 2019). The Jordanian public universities have also been able to offer services and products to their workers and students at any willing prices hence it has become a priority to many students and workers as compared to the private universities in Jordan.

How Quality Advantage can be used by the Jordanian Public Universities in achievement of Competitive Advantage

Quality advantage is quite important for the Jordanian Public Universities because it enables supervisors, employees, and managers in such institutions to reduce or minimize avoidable costs associated with quality and how to apply the —customer based criteria “in measuring the quality of work done. In essence, the use of quality advantage helps organizations to achieve competitive advantages because it teaches supervisors and managers on not only how to analyze data and information but also on how to measure and even enhance work processes continuously (Ali, 2018). Quality is quite important because it helps in the satisfaction of customers as well as ensuring that their loyalty is retained thus making

customers to continue associating with organizations. Public universities in Jordan should aim at using the philosophy and tools of world class institutions in order to achieve competitive advantages. This is because quality advantage is known to emphasize on the—quality process management—which is also a function of the effectiveness of such organizations. This is because quality advantage focuses more on the global impact of competition, the benefits that are associated with the implementation of quality in the entire organization as well as the continuous costs of the defects. The operations of public universities should therefore be designed with an aim of achieving excellence at all times and at all places. It was noted that just like the other businesses entities, public universities in Jordan also operated in highly competitive markets. This implies that they also have to take on and see off their rivals (Al Shobaki & Abu-Naser, 2017). It is therefore important for these institutions of higher learning to make decisions on how best they can effectively operate in such competitive environments and gain competitive advantages. This is quite true since not all organizations come up with similar answers and for good reasons. It is therefore prudent for the Jordanian public universities to ascertain viable ways through which they can easily gain competitive advantages especially in the wake of the private universities that have given public universities a run for their money. That apart, it is also prudent for public universities to pay their respective strengths just like other business entities do since not all the universities in Jordan possess similar strengths.

This is also based on the fact that majority of the markets in Jordan may be segmented and therefore this implies that what is more vital to a specific segment may actually be lesser vital to another set of segments (Sanusi, Sumiyati, Winata & Hakim, 2020). It is therefore important for the Jordanian public universities to decide on the appropriate market segments that they are targeting. As earlier on discussed, there are various ways through which the HRM departments in the Jordanian Public universities can achieve a competitive advantage and among these include through offering clients lowers prices and even through offering them with products and services that are superior and affordable prices. In addition to that, public universities in Jordan can also be in a better position of gaining competitive advantages through quicker delivery of products and through the provision of —superior customer | service to their clients. One sure way through which the public universities in Jordan can achieve a competitive advantage is through putting more concentration on offering quality services and products to students and other viable stakeholders that the institutions serve in their day to day endeavors. This implies that there is need for these institutions to offer its customers with not only products and services of higher quality but also at prices which are premium as compare to the private universities. This is quite true since at most times than not, quality is usually associated or linked to consistency (Putri & Yuniawan, 2016). This is also because customers who are happy with the first experiences that are provided by public universities and whose wants and needs have been effectively satisfied will mostly likely appreciate being associated with the universities and will even them to their friends and relatives as being the best. Quality should therefore be provided to stakeholders not only this time but also next time and every time (Alshawabkeh et al. 2019). It was noted that customers who highly cared about being provided with higher quality were even more willing of paying more in order to get such good or high-

quality services despite of the additional expenses.

Previous studies

(Sadiqi, 2022) Strategic Management of Human Resources as an Entry Point to Achieve Competitive Advantage in the Enterprise: Mobiles Telecom Case Study.

This study aims to determine the nature of the relationship between strategic management of human resources and competitive advantage. Bashar, since access to competitive advantage is largely linked to the application of a strategic perspective related to human resource because it can be a strengths or weaknesses, strategic management of human resources has become an essential reference for many of the world's successful institutions seeking to achieve a continuous and lasting competitive advantage. The descriptive and analytical curriculum was relied upon and identified as a key tool for data collection and analysis through the statistical programmer (spss) to test hypotheses using a range of statistical methods, the results have shown an impact of strategic human resources management in achieving competitive advantage at Mobilis Telecommunications, through human resources management policy and functions (Planning, polarization, recruitment and selection, training, motivation and compensation) This is explained by the R2 determination coefficient that came in equal to 0.932 This indicates that 93.2% of the change in competitive advantage is due to the change in strategic management of human resources.

(Al-Ghdabi, 2019) The Impact of Human Resource Management Practices on Sustainable Competitive Advantage: A Study of Service Enterprises in Jordan

The purpose of this study is threefold. First, to investigate the total impact of HRM practices on SCA. Second, to explore the impact of HRM practices, i.e., knowledge of business, delivery of human resources and management of change on SCA. Third, to examine the impact of HRM practices an entire construct on the dimensions of SCA, i.e., positive value, rareness, imitability, and organization. A descriptive analytical research method was adopted for the sake of the current study. A questionnaire was distributed to a sample of 195 managers, from which a total of 187 complete questionnaires were returned to be analyzed via IBM SPSS and AMOS®. The results revealed that HRM practices had a significant effect on SCA. Particularly, knowledge of business, delivery of human resources and management of change as dimensions of HRM used in the current study had significant effects on SCA. Moreover, HRM practices as an entire construct was found to exert significant effect on all dimensions of SCA

DISCUSS THE CONCLUSIONS

Hypothesis 1.1: There is statistically significant impact of the HRM practices (Planning, Recruitment and selection, Training and Developing, Compensation and wages, Performance management) on the Low-Cost Leadership advantage in the Governmental Jordanian Universities.

To test the first hypothesis, we can use the results of the estimated regression as shown in

Table (1). The estimated coefficient for planning of human resources is positive and significant at 5% level ($\beta_1=0.757$, $\rho<0.0001$) the estimated coefficient for recruitment and selection of human resources is positive and significant at 5% level ($\beta_2=0.250$, $\rho<0.0001$) the estimated coefficient for training and development of human resources is positive and significant at 5% level). The estimated coefficient for compensation and wages of human resources is positive and significant at 5% level ($\beta_3=0.298$, $\rho<0.0001$) The estimated coefficient for compensation and wages of human resources is positive and significant at 5% level ($\beta_4=1.251$, $\rho<0.0001$) The estimated coefficient for compensation and wages of human resources is positive and significant at 5% level ($\beta_5=0.541$, $\rho<0.0001$). (. We can see that all regression coefficients are significant since all p-values are less than 0.05. This means that HRM practices have positive and significant impact on cost leadership which supports Hypothesis 1.1. The standardized coefficient tells us that the important driver for cost leadership advantage is compensation and wages of human resources because it has the largest standardized coefficient (0.525) and the least important driver is training and development (0.127).

Table 1: Estimated regression coefficients (standard error)

Independent variable	Parameter	Unstandardized coefficient	Standard error	Standardized coefficient	p-value
Intercept	B0	-8.149	0.586		<.0001
Planning	B1	0.757	0.070	0.376	<.0001
Recruitment and selection	B2	0.250	0.066	0.131	<.0001
Training and development	B3	0.298	0.082	0.127	<.0001
Compensation and wages	B4	1.251	0.083	0.525	<.0001
Performance assessment	B5	0.541	0.077	0.244	<.0001

Hypothesis 1.2: There is no statistically significant impact of the HRM practices (Planning, Recruitment and selection, Training and Developing, Compensation and wages, Performance management) on the quality advantage in the Governmental Jordanian Universities.

To test the second hypothesis, we can use the results of the estimated regression coefficients as shown in Table 2. The estimated coefficient for planning of human resources is positive and significant at 5% level ($\beta_1=0.758$, $\rho<0.0001$). The estimated coefficient for recruitment and selection of human resources is positive and significant at 5% level ($\beta_2=0.461$, $\rho<0.0001$). The estimated coefficient for training and development of human resources is positive and significant at 5% level ($\beta_3=0.232$, $\rho<0.0001$). The estimated coefficient for compensation and wages of human resources is positive and significant at 5% level ($\beta_4=0.183$, $\rho<0.0001$). The estimated coefficient for performance assessment of human resources is positive and significant at 5% level ($\beta_5=0.552$, $\rho<0.0001$). We can see that all regression coefficients are significant since all p-values are less than 0.05. This means that HRM practices have positive and significant impact on quality advantage which supports Hypothesis 1.2. The standardized coefficient tells us that the important driver for quality advantage is planning of human resources because it has the largest standardized coefficient (0.482) and the least important driver is compensation and wages (0.098).

Table 2: Estimated regression coefficients (standard error)

Independent variable	Parameter	Unstandardized coefficient	Standard error	Standardized coefficient	p-value
Intercept	B0	-4.995	0.448		<.0001
Planning	B1	0.758	0.053	0.482	<.0001
Recruitment and selection	B2	0.641	0.051	0.429	<.0001
Training and development	B3	0.232	0.063	0.126	<.0001
Compensation and wages	B4	0.183	0.063	0.098	<.0001
Performance assessment	B5	0.552	0.060	0.341	<.0001

Hypothesis 1.3: There is no statistically significant impact of the HRM practices (Planning, Recruitment and selection, Training and Developing, Compensation and wages, Performance management) on the Differentiation advantage in the Governmental Jordanian Universities.

To test the third hypothesis, we can use the results of the estimated regression coefficients as shown in Table 3. The estimated coefficient for planning of human resources is positive and significant at 5% level ($\beta_1=0.197$, $\rho<0.0001$). The estimated coefficient for recruitment and selection of human resources is positive and significant at 5% level ($\beta_2=0.673$, $\rho<0.0001$). The estimated coefficient for training and development of human resources is positive and significant at 5% level ($\beta_3=0.747$, $\rho<0.0001$).

The estimated coefficient for compensation and wages of human resources is positive and significant at 5% level ($\beta_4=0.263$, $\rho<0.0001$). The estimated coefficient for performance assessment of human resources is positive and significant at 5% level ($\beta_5=0.402$, $\rho<0.0001$). We can see that all regression coefficients are significant since all p-values are less than 0.05. This means that HRM practices have positive and significant impact on differentiation advantage which supports Hypothesis 1.3.

The standardized coefficient tells us that the important driver for differentiation advantage is recruitment and selection of human resources because it has the largest standardized coefficient (0.480) and the least important driver is planning (0.134).

Table 3: Estimated regression coefficients (standard error)

Independent variable	Parameter	Unstandardized coefficient	Standard error	Standardized coefficient	p-value
Intercept	B0	-4.690	0.440		<.0001
Planning	B1	0.197	0.052	0.134	<.0001
Recruitment and selection	B2	0.673	0.050	0.480	<.0001
Training and development	B3	0.747	0.061	0.433	<.0001
Compensation and wages	B4	0.263	0.062	0.151	<.0001
Performance assessment	B5	0.402	0.058	0.248	<.0001

Conclusions

The study investigated the impact of Human Resource best practices including planning, recruitment and selection, training and development, compensation and wages, and performance management on the competitive advantage in the governmental Jordanian universities. The quantitative multiple regression analysis enabled an examination of the relationship between these variables where HRM practices are treated as the independent variable and competitive advantages are treated as the dependent variables. This approach was found appropriate to be fitted for the observed data since the assumptions of regression model such as no multicollinearity, model residuals are normally distributed, having constant variance, and no autocorrelation were met.

Therefore, the results from fitting multiple linear regression model yielded trusted or reliable inferences. In total, we fit five different regression models since there are five dependent variables of competitive advantages, i.e. low-cost leadership, differentiation advantage, quality advantage, considered in this study. All models using the same independent variables.

All regression models show satisfactory model to the observed data. The five independent variables included in the regression models are able to explain approximately half of total variability in competitive advantages. These five independent variables are also found to have positive and significant impact on competitive advantages. Based on these findings all hypotheses were supported and accepted. The first hypothesis is supported. The estimated regression coefficient for planning, recruitment and selection, training and development, compensation and wages, and performance management based on regression equation with cost leadership as the dependent variable are 0.757, 0.250, 0.298, 1.251, and 0.541, respectively. This shows that HRM practices have positive and significant impact on low-cost leadership at 5% level. The standardized regression coefficient indicates that the top three important drivers for cost leadership advantage is compensation and wages, planning, and performance assessment of human resources.

The second hypothesis is supported. The estimated regression coefficient for planning, recruitment and selection, training and development, compensation and wages, and performance management based on regression equation with quality advantage as the dependent variable are 0.758, 0.641, 0.232, 0.183, and 0.479, respectively. This shows that HRM practices have positive and significant impact on quality advantage at 5% level. The standardized regression coefficient indicates that the top three important drivers for quality advantage are planning, recruitment and selection, and performance assessment of human resources. The third hypothesis is supported. The estimated regression coefficient for planning, recruitment and selection, training and development, compensation and wages, and performance management based on regression equation with differentiation advantage as the dependent variable are 0.197, 0.673, 0.747, 0.263, and 0.402, respectively. This shows that HRM practices have positive and significant impact on differentiation advantage at 5% level. The standardized regression coefficient indicates that the top three important drivers for

differentiation advantage are recruitment and selection, training and development, and performance assessment of human resources.

All of these findings have shown that this research model is beneficial and can greatly help the HRM to make better strategies for the Jordanian Public Universities in terms of improving competitive advantages. In addition, the results also indicate that HRM practices play an important role in competitive advantages therefore institution should embrace viable HRM functions so that Jordanian Public Universities are capable to maintain competitive advantage by investing through numerous human resource activities such as selection, recruitment, training, and the rewarding of institutional personnel.

The conclusive findings are listed below based on the research.

- HRM practices have positive and significant impact on low-cost leadership
- HRM practices have positive and significant impact on response speed feature. Showing that the compensation, training and development, performance management systems have a role in improving the efficiency of the employees.
- HRM practices have positive and significant impact on differentiation advantage, offering the firms with unique benefits.
- HRM practices play an important role in competitive advantages and can help the firms get better results.
- HRM policies therefore present an opportunity for the organization to frame suitable policies and produce better leaders and more satisfied workforce that can provide competitive advantage to the firm.

Recommendations

- The external factors such as cultural, social, environmental, political and government policy-based can be added to the research for understanding the HRM 's role in their influence.
- The qualitative methods of research include emotional and subjective matters and therefore are of significance for the research. Therefore, the researches in future must use qualitative or a mix of qualitative and quantitative methods to bring more reliability to the research.
- Direct face to face interviews can provide deeper insights into the experiences and opinions of the employees and HR professionals. Therefore, the later researches can include interview-based methods for primary data collection.
- The feedback of other stakeholders involved in the process can also be included to understand the challenges of HR policy making and the balancing act that is needed.
- Lastly, with the change in generation, the mindset of the young workforce changes along with their priorities. It is therefore required that a trend of changing notions about the HRM practices must be developed to understand the complete impact and assessment.

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